

Impact of Extroversion Personality Trait on Female's Role in Medical Institutions of Pakistan: A Case Study of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS)

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Abstract

Human personality dimensions or personality traits have great influence on people's relationships, goals achievements and professional success both positively and negatively. Extraversion is the personality trait refers to the tendency to enjoy and communicate being with people (Turner, 2007). Clustering of female are found in medical professional universities and they are working side by side with male. However, their role particularly, at higher teaching and decision making positions are limited. Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro is the first public sector medical professional university in Pakistan. This medical university playing a leadership role in standardizing medical education in country therefore, selected as sample medical professional institution in Pakistan. In this study researcher analyze sample females on extroversion personality trait, to explore the specific role that personality trait might play in female professional role with special focus on Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS). Under extraversion personality trait, extroverts and introverts are the two different personalities and study results shows that in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS) both extroverts and introverts female were found. Empirical analysis also confirmed that extroversion personality traits has significant impact on female's involvement in functioning of medical university, which in turn effect their role in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS).

Key Words: Personality Trait, Medical, Profession, Extroverts, Introverts, Human, Management, Functioning

1. Introduction

The economic prosperity of nations depends on effective and efficient utilization of human resource but educated female as active and efficient human resource not fully utilized during last decades in professional institutions in Pakistan (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2011). Medical professional universities supposed to be the traditional subject based institutions for females. Now females equally or more than male, enrolled in medical field and working side by side with their male colleagues however, their roles in functioning of medical institutions remain undermine. The decades of research on personality found that human personality plays vital role in their career advancement. Extroversion personality trait consider as the foundation pillar of personality analysis. In this research paper, extroversion personality trait used as an important tool to analyze female personalities who were working in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS). Study also explores the specific role that extroversion personality traits might play in female job performance in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS). This research paper is divided into three different sections. Section one based on introduction and review literature. Section two shows methodology of study and last section presents findings, conclusions and recommendations.

2. Literature Review

Medical is reported as female dominating field of study (Syeda et al., 2006). According to United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization Institute for Statistics (2011), in United Kingdom, United State of America, Bahrain, Oman and Iran ratio of female graduates in health and welfare sector is 80 percent, 82 percent, 83 percent, 78 percent and 72 percent respectively. Whereas, female representation at senior teaching, management and decision making positions in professional institutions is very low. According to Federal Bureau of Statistics of Pakistan (2011), female enrolment ratio in Medical Colleges is 56 percent and as faculty is 29 percent. Over past decade's gender distribution of staff, in professional universities experiencing a positive change in Pakistan and all over the world, but still there is a decline in the representation of female

from junior to senior academic positions and gender gap that favors males more widely pronounced in higher education management even in female dominating field of study (Social Policy and Development Center, 2009).

Personality dimensions or personality traits have great influence on people's relations, goals accomplishments, and professional success (Bovee et al., 1993). Singh 2002, reported that female personality also play an important role in female's career advancement in professional institutions. The word personality has been described by various personality analysts (i.e. Luthans, 1992, Eysenck 1991, Digman, 1990, Barrett and Pietromonaco, 1997, Bovee et al., 1993 and so on) within many dimensions. In broad sense personality is the combination of response patterns of an individual such as attitudinal, emotional and behavioral. Extraversion is the fundamental trait of human personality, it is the act or state of being predominantly concerned with and obtaining gratification from what is outside the self (Caligiuri, 2000). The broad dimensional trait extraversion is refer to the tendency to enjoy being with people and often perceived as full of energy and people having this trait is highly associated with engagement with the external world (Eysenck 1991). Extraversion personality trait has two different dimensions that is extraverts and introverts (Digman, 1990 and Matthews et al., 2003). Extraverts peoples characterized by positive emotions, they tend to be enthusiastic, action-oriented individuals who avail the opportunities for excitement (Digman, 1990). They take pleasure in activities that involve large social gatherings this includes parties, community activities and business/political groups (Goldberg 1990). Extroverts become energized when people are around them in contrast, getting bored if they are alone. In groups they like to talk, assert themselves, and draw attention to themselves, their way of behaving often remain relaxed, this gives impression to others that they are very confident in themselves and have a great self-image which may not necessarily the case (Barrett and Pietromonaco, 1997). Extraverts are understandable and accessible; they act first and think later (Bono & Judge, 2004). Caligiuri (2000) found that, relative to introvert personality the extrovert person was evaluated better in interactions with colleagues and in terms of work performance. The reasons are that extrovert having more willing to speak actively with their local subordinates and boss than do introvert expatriates. According to Bono & Judge (2004) extraverts are positive, ambitious and influential; they are likely to generate confidence and enthusiasm among followers. At work place extroverts like working with others peoples and seek variety, action and achievement and having an optimistic view of the future (Higgins et al., 2007). Therefore, it is stated that extrovert's personalities show visible leadership qualities. In contrast, introversion is referring to the tendency to being predominantly concerned with and interested in person's own mental life (Eysenck 1991). Introverts personalities less involved in the social world, they tend to seem quiet, low-key and deliberate (Barrett and Pietromonaco, 1997). According to Digman (1990) their lack of social involvement should not be concenter as shyness or depression in other words introverts personalities simply need less stimulation than extraverts and prefer to spend more time alone infect, they feel uncomfortable if they spend too much time focusing on other people. Introverts are less outgoing and less sociable but they may be very active and energetic however, regarding concepts and ideas their energy comes from their inside (Eysenck 1991). Introverts personalities have smaller group of friends and they enjoy interacting with close friends, often introverts feel pleasure in solitary activities such as watching television, reading, writing and using computers (Caligiuri, 2000). Introverts personalities are more passive therefore; just want to understand the world rather than trying to change (Barrett and Pietromonaco, 1997). Introverts think deeply about the matters and things but their attitude is reserved and they posses impenetrable personality, they are supposed to be less spontaneous in social situations therefore; first they think and observed the situations before acting in social situation (Mount and Barrick, 1995). Often introverts prefer to concentrate on a single activity at a time therefore they feel uncomfortable to do multiple works at a time and prefer to do work that has depth; they like to do work alone and seek quiet for concentration (Huang et al., 2005). In the light of review litterateur regarding introverts personalities, it is stated that extrovert's personalities short of leadership qualities. In terms of gender, female are supposed to be a reserved personality, less socialized and careful in communication (i.e. their personal characteristics) which effects on their personal and professional life. It is supposedly those females are not able to manage crises situation and they lack of decision making power therefore, poorly represented at decision making positions (Lizzarage, 2007). Luthans (1992) argued that

networking and socializing had a significant relationship with professional success but female by nature is less communicative, less socialized and more reserved with their job fellows which in turned limited their networks at workplace. According to Shah (1999) female by nature found as reserved personality that is an obstacle which keep female as undermine factor in human resource management.

The above discussion on personality indicates that extroversion personality trait of female have significant impact in their career advancement. Clustering of female are found in medical profession but they are limited at senior professional positions in their traditional subject based universities. This opens the area to investigate the females' role in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS) and to analyze their personalities as to find out their personality impacts on their career advancement.

3. Methodology

Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro playing a leadership role in standardizing medical education in Pakistan. Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro selected to see special trends of female role in professional institution which is supposed to be traditional course based (i.e. medical) institution for female. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Secondary data collected from administration office of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro (LUMHS). In order to test suppositions, primary data was collected through focused group interviews by structured and unstructured methods. Raosoft sample size calculator was used to determine the sample size of respondent and 98 female teaching & managing staff (including Deans, Hostel Provost, Heads of Departments etc) was selected from Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro (LUMHS), to collect the data through questionnaire. In this research study, beside formal statistical approaches researcher applied simple and logistic regression techniques for prediction; researcher also used MS Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to analyze the data and to present the findings.

4. Study Results

Liaquat University of Medical Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro is one of the oldest medical degrees awarding institution in Pakistan. This university plays a leadership role in standardizing medical education in the country, on the other side university has remarkable contribution in provision of health care facilities. Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro accommodates 519 male and female students (Director of Admission and Registrar Office Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, 2013-14). The yearly intake of medical students in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro has been improved during last decade. Clustering of female students in medical fields makes encouraging female enrolment ratio in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro. Figure 1 shows fluctuating male-female enrolment trends and highlights that during past years female enrolment significantly improved and becomes more than male.

Figure-1: Male-Female Enrolment in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro n= 15 (%)

Source: Director of Admissions Office, Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro, 2013-14 (Before 2001-02 status of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro was served as Medical College)

In Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro at academic cadre female faculty perform multiple duties. Female faculty participates at all academic positions (this includes professors, assistant professors, associate professors, senior and junior lecturers) and providing their services for research promotion and research production. In addition female professors, assistant professors and associate professors also perform their health care duties in those hospitals which are attached with Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS) Jamshoro (i.e. Liaquat University Hospital, Jamshoro and Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad). In Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro female faculty also provides their professional services to meet the healthcare needs of the community. Therefore they are also involved in free medical camping activities (this includes flood victims etc) as for the welfare of other needy peoples. Figure 2 indicates that beside performed various tasks to achieve related with teaching, research and health care, female faculty representation at academic cadre in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS) Jamshoro is not equal to men.

Figure-2: Male-Female Academic Representation in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro (%) n=12

Source: Registrar Office Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro, 2013-14

In Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS) Jamshoro, administration structure includes Governor of Province performs function of Chancellor of University, Minister of Health serve as Pro-Chancellor. The management cadre headed by a Vice-Chancellor of the university. There is no Pro-Vice Chancellor as to assist the Vice-Chancellor in university academic and management work. Registrar, Controller of examination, Director of Finance, Director of Admission, Director of Planning and Development, Director of Research/Postgraduate, Deans, Directors, Principal (Institute of Dentistry) and Chairpersons of Teaching Departments etc perform their management responsibilities as to manage university related affairs. In this medical institute females are participating at various management positions, such as Heads of Teaching Departments, Director of Admission, Hostel Provost, Deputy Hostel Provost, Protocol Office, and Secretary to Vice Chancellor as well as female role in clinical management cannot be ignored. Whereas, figure 3 shows that female representation at management cadre in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS) Jamshoro is not encouraging. In Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS) Jamshoro female are performing heavy work load management responsibilities as Dean of Faculty and Clinical Unit In charges. However, at management level female limited her into few management positions and remain under used resource at decision making and policy formulation key positions such as Vice-Chancellor, Registrar, Controller of Examination, Director of Graduate Studies etc.

Figure-3: Male-Female Participation at Management Cadre in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro n=12 (%)

Source: Registrar Office Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro, 2013-14

Management positions includes Vice-Chancellor, Pro-Vice-Chancellor, Registrar, Controller of Examinations, Director of Research/Post Graduate Studies, Deans, Director of Finance, Director Of Planning & Development, Director Admissions, Director of Sports, Directors/Chairperson of departments, Deputy Director/Advisor/Chief Planning & Development, Librarian, Additional Registrar, Director of I.T & Additional controller & Deputy Registrars.

Table 1 highlights that 44.7 percent (i.e. strongly agree and agree combined) sample female working at academic and management in sample universities were reserved persons; they tend to seem quiet, low-key and deliberate. In addition, 27.3 percent (i.e. disagree and strongly disagree combined) sample female were less involved in the social activities. These working female were not shy or depress infect, they were very active and energetic but simply not socially, they needs less stimulation and more time alone, this indicative of introverts personality under Big Five Factors. These female lacks of communication initiatives which are the required quality for effective leadership. Furthermore, data reveals that 51 percent (i.e. disagree and strongly disagree combined) sample female reported that they were not reserved persons, in groups these female like to talk, assert themselves, and draw attention to them.

Table-1: Female on Extraversion Personality Trait in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS) n = 98 (%)

Statements	1	2	3	4	5	Total
I see myself as someone who is reserved	6	34	–	42	18	100
I see myself as someone who is outgoing, sociable	20	40	10	24	6	100

Source: Survey Data, 2013-14

➤ 1=Strongly Agree , 2=Agree, 3=Undecided, 4=Disagree , 5=Strongly Disagree

In addition, 62.7 percent (i.e. strongly agree and agree combined) were engaged with the external world, they enjoy being with people, and are perceived as full of energy, they have tendency to seek out stimulation and the company of others, they were enthusiastic, action-oriented female, this indicative of extraverts personality under Big Five Factors. These female found to be major initiative taking personalities. These extroverts female were capable and have guts to take leadership positions. There was someone (i.e. undecided) who was not able to analyze their personality on account of extraversion personality trait.

Table-2: Empirical Analysis of Personality Impact on Numbers of Research Publications by Sample Female n = 98

Personality Traits	Un-Standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.362	1.699		-.213	0.832
Introversion (X ₂)	3.696	1.612	.235	2.292	0.024*

Source: Survey Data, 2013-14

*Significant, p > 0.05

Dependent variable (Y) = numbers of research publications in journals

Table 2 presents the impact of introversion personality trait (i.e. independent variable) on numbers of research publications in journals (i.e. dependent variable) by sample female. Significant value of t-statistic (i.e. 2.292) shows that introversion personality traits has significant impact on research publications by sample female. This indicative that sample female who are less involved in social world and like to experience new thing are more likely to publish research papers. Positive values of b coefficient for introversion (i.e. 3.696) personality trait indicates that variable have direct relationship with numbers of research publications by sample female.

Table-3: Empirical Analysis of Personality Impact on Conferences Organized by Sample Female n = 98

Personality Trait	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig.	Exp(b)
Introversion (X ₁)	.316	.455	.481	.488	1.371
Extraversion (X ₂)	1.404	.482	8.497	.004*	4.070
Constant	-1.238	.469	6.966	.008*	.290

Source: Survey Data, 2013-14

Dependent Variable (Y)=conferences organized by sample female

1= conference organized throughout their professional career

0= for not a single conference organized throughout their professional career

*=Significant, p > 0.01

Table 3 presents the impact of introversion and extroversion personality traits on sample female involvement in management activities. To analyze the impact of personality on female participation in management activities, conferences organized by sample female selected as independent variable. “1” is allocated for conference organized throughout their professional career and “0” allocated for not a single conference organized by sample female throughout their professional career. The significant value of Wald statistics for extraversion personality trait (i.e. 8.497) indicates that extroverts sample female like to get in management activities. Introvert personality trait has not statistically significant impact on female involvement in conferences organizing for their institutions. The value of Exp (b) for extraversion personality trait (i.e. 4.070) indicates that those sample female who are extroverts have more motivation to be involved in management activities.

5. Conclusions & Recommendations

It is concluded that female enrolment ratio in medical professional institutions is encouraging however, their role in functioning of professional medical institutions particularly, at senior teaching and administrative positions remain unsatisfactory. Extraversion personality trait has considerable impact on job performance of working females. Therefore, in this study extraversion personality trait is used to analyze the sample females' personalities who were working at teaching and administrative positions in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS). Study results shows that on extraversion personality trait 57 percent sample females fall under extrovert personality trait. These females found to be major initiative taking personalities unlike introverts. These extrovert females were courageous and competent enough to take leadership roles. In contrast, 36 percent sample women reported as introverts, these women lacked communication initiative and short by required quality for effective leadership therefore, poorly involved at key decision making positions in sample medical university. Empirical analysis also confirmed that personality traits has significant impact on females' involvement in functioning of medical university, which in turn effect their representation at academic and management cadre in Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS).

To enhance female role in functioning of medical professional universities, it is necessary at policy levels, to encourage more female at all senior teaching and decision making positions. There should be a policy to ensure female's equal participation (i.e. bottom to top management) in professional medical universities. It is recommended that personality development sessions should be held for enhancing females' personalities, their management potentials and their self-motivation, to work at decision making positions in professional medical universities institutions in Pakistan. More opportunities for training, workshops, management based short

courses should be provided for female. It is recommended to establish more separate medical professional institutions for female, as a positive step towards providing more opportunities to strongly play their roles in functioning of their institutions.

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